

High-Spin Manganese(II) Complexes with 1-Propyl Imidazole

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A number of spin-free complexes of manganese(II) were prepared with 1-propyl imidazole. The complexes prepared were of the type MnL_nX_n ($n=2, X=Cl, Br, NCS$; $n=4, X=NCS$; $n=6, X=Cl, Br, I, NO_2, ClO_4, BF_4$) and $[Mn_2N][MnLCl_4]$. The complexes which have either octahedral, distorted octahedral or tetrahedral stereochemistries were characterised by elemental analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, i.r. and U. V. spectral measurements. Fungicidal test for the ligand and some of the complexes with the fungi *Curvularia* and *Helminthosporium sativum* showed that in both cases the fungicidal activity of the ligands invariably decreased on coordination to the metal.

IMIDAZOLE plays an important role in complex biological systems. As a part of systematic studies¹ on imidazole and its derivatives, we report here the complexes of 1-propyl imidazole with manganese(II). All the complexes reported here were found to be spin-free manganese(II) complexes with five unpaired electrons and they have been characterised by elemental analysis, conductivity and magnetic susceptibility data at room temperature, electronic and vibrational spectra. The fungicidal tests were performed in order to find out the effect of ligation on the fungicidal activity of the ligands, and to find out the possibility of using these compounds as antifungal reagents.

Experimental

The 1-propyl imidazole ligand (L) was supplied by B. A. S. F. (Ludwigshafen, Germany). The hydrated $MnCl_2$, $Mn(NO_3)_2$ were from B. D. H. Hydrated $MnBr_2$, $Mn(ClO_4)_2$ were prepared from $MnCO_3$ by reacting with HBr and $HClO_4$ respectively. $Mn(NCS)_2$, $Mn(BF_4)_2$ and MnI_2 were prepared by reacting hydrated $Mn(NO_3)_2$ with appropriate alkali metal salts. The metal was estimated gravimetrically as $MnNH_4PO_4 \cdot H_2O$, the halides and the SCN^- as their silver salts and the NO_3^- , ClO_4^- and BF_4^- (X) were determined gravimetrically as their nitron salts, $C_{20}H_{16}N_4 \cdot HX$.^{2,3}

Electronic spectra, i.r. spectra, electrical conductivity and magnetic susceptibility were determined as described previously¹.

Thermal decomposition studies were carried out by heating the sample in an air oven at 120-130° to constant weight. The product so obtained was characterised as usual.

Fungicidal test of some compounds were carried out taking two different fungi, e.g., *Curvularia* and *Helminthosporium sativum*. The test was carried

out by preparing the Potato-Dextrose medium. To the medium the fungus was added called reference and to another conical flask containing the medium both fungus and compound were added, called test medium. The reference and test-medium were kept in an incubator for six days and then filtered separately. From the weight the percentage of inhibition was calculated using the formula

$$\% \text{ of inhibition} = \frac{Y-X}{Y} \times 100$$

X = growth in test-medium
Y = growth in the reference.

The experiment was carried out at a concentration of 500 ppm.

Syntheses of Complexes :

The hexakis complexes were prepared by reacting appropriate metal salt with ligand in 1 : 6 molar proportion in ethanol medium and stirring. The compound obtained was filtered, washed several times with alcohol, then ether and dried in *vacuo*.

The tetrakis thiocyanate complex was prepared by reacting $Mn(NCS)_2$ and the ligand in 1 : 4 molar proportions and stirring magnetically for some time. All attempts to prepare the hexakis complex even by using too much excess of the ligand failed.

This compound was obtained by heating the MnL_2Cl_2 in an air oven at 120-130° to constant weight. The percentage loss observed was 55.78 (Th 55.99%).

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MnL₆Br₂

This compound was obtained from MnL₆Br₂ as above. Percentage loss observed was 49.48 (Th. 50.28%)

MnL₆(NCS)₂

The compound was obtained from MnL₆(NCS)₂. The percentage loss observed was 36.04 (Th. 36.00%).

By similar methods, MnL₆X₂ (X=I, NO₃, ClO₄, BF₄), on thermolysis at 120° decomposes to give brown or black residues whose stoichiometry could not be established.

Results and Discussion

The compounds prepared are reported in Table 1, alongwith their m.p., colour, analytical data, conductivity and magnetic moment data. All the complexes reported here are of high-spin type. Though the magnetic moment for high-spin Mn(II) with five unpaired electrons is 5.92 B.M⁴, the

mechanism where the dissociation of ligand molecules from the coordination sphere on dissolution in a solvent takes place, perhaps leading to an equilibrium of the type

The i. r. spectra of all the complexes were measured from 4000-500 cm⁻¹ in Nujol mull. Definite evidences were obtained regarding the mode of bonding of the polyatomic anions around the central metal ion. For MnL₆(NCS)₂ the ν(C≡N) was observed at 2060 cm⁻¹ and ν(C-S) at 770 cm⁻¹ indicating terminal coordination through hard N-end of the thiocyanate group^{7,8}. The i.r. spectra of MnL₆(NCS)₂ could not be taken due to the extreme hygroscopic nature of the compound. For the [MnL₆](BF₄)₂ complex, unsplit ν₃ and ν₄ bands were obtained in the 1050-1140 and 640 cm⁻¹ region respectively, indicating the presence of ionic tetrafluoroborate⁹ (T_g). In the [MnL₆](ClO₄)₂ a broad strong band at 1150-1050 cm⁻¹ (ν₈) and a sharp band at 640 cm⁻¹ (ν₄) indicating ionic perchlorate^{10, 11} (T_g) was obtained.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, M. P., COLOUR, CONDUCTIVITY AND MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUES OF MANGANESE(II) COMPLEXES WITH 1-PROPYL IMIDAZOLE (L)

Compound	Colour	M.P. (°C)	Analyses (%) [*]		ΔM in Acetone ^{**} (Ω ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹ cm ²)	μ _{eff} ^{**} (B.M.)
			Metal	Anion		
MnL ₆ Cl ₂	Chocolate	Liquid	15.6(15.9)	20.1(20.5)	Insol.	—
MnL ₆ Cl ₂	White	80	6.6(7.0)	9.2(9.0)	23.1	—
MnL ₆ Br ₂	Black	Liquid	12.3(12.6)	36.5(36.8)	4.3 ^(a)	6.0
MnL ₆ Br ₂	White	143	6.2(6.3)	18.1(18.2)	55	—
MnL ₆ I ₂	White	149	5.7(5.7)	26.9(26.2)	38.4	5.8
MnL ₆ (NCS) ₂	Yellow	—	13.8(14.1)	28.7(29.7)	11.9 ^(a)	—
MnL ₆ (NCS) ₂	White	70	8.8(9.0)	18.0(19.0)	123	—
MnL ₆ (NO ₃) ₂	White	90	6.4(6.5)	13.3(14.8)	34.96	5.8
MnL ₆ (ClO ₄) ₂	White	90	5.6(6.0)	19.5(21.8)	16.1	—
MnL ₆ (BF ₄) ₂	White	78	6.5(6.2)	19.2(19.5)	7.8 ^(a)	5.8
[Me ₄ N][MnLCl ₆]	White	>240	15.9(15.9)	30.0(30.8) ^(c)	258.8	5.8
					133	5.8
					50.2 ^(a)	—
					191.3 ^(b)	6.1

* Theoretical values in brackets ** Measurements at room temperature
(a) Nitromethane (b) Nitrobenzene (c) %Cl

reported magnetic moment values for Mn(II) complexes varies from 5.6-6.10 B.M.⁵

The conductivity measurements in dilute solution (~10⁻³M) of Me₂CO, PhNO₂ and MeNO₂ at room temperature showed⁶ that the hexakis complexes of the type MnL₆X₂ (X=BF₄, ClO₄) behaved as 1 : 2 electrolytes and [Me₄N] [MnLCl₆] behaved as a 1 : 1 electrolyte. All other complexes showed non-electrolytic behaviour. It was rather surprising to find that MnL₆(NO₃)₂ complex behaved as a non-electrolyte, though on the basis of vibrational spectroscopy, presence of uncoordinated, ionic NO₃⁻(D_{3h}) was clearly established. This anomaly can be rationalised by proposing a

The nitrate complex, [MnL₆](NO₃)₂ showed a strong N—O stretching mode at 1390 cm⁻¹ (ν₂) region and two i.r. active deformation modes at 830 cm⁻¹ (ν₂) and 730 cm⁻¹ (ν₄). These bands indicated free, uncoordinated NO₃⁻ ion having D_{3h} symmetry^{1,2-1,4}.

The electronic spectra were taken either in acetone or methanol. The complexes showed a weak absorption band around 30,000-33,000 cm⁻¹. The ground state for octahedral Mn(II) is ⁶A_{1g} which is the only sextet level present making all the transitions weak due to their spin-forbidden nature^{1,5}. However, in some cases observed absorptions may be due to vibronic coupling^{1,5}.

Invariably the tetrahedral manganese(II) compounds show a more intense band than the octahedral compounds, due to the mixing of metal *p* and *d* orbitals. But no such phenomena was observed for our complexes, which may be due to the loss of the tetrahedral structures of the compounds on dissolution.

Fungicidal tests were carried out at 500 ppm with two fungi namely *Curvularia* and *Helminthosporium sativum*. It is seen that the activity of the compounds invariably decreased on coordination. The percentage of inhibition of the ligand and some of the compounds is given in Table 2.

TABLE-2 : FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY OF 1-PROPYL IMIDAZOLE(L) AND SOME OF ITS MN(II) COMPLEXES

Test Samples	% of inhibition Fungus "Cur"	% of inhibition Fungus "HS"
L	68.0	72.7
MnL ₆ Cl ₂	17.3	10
MnL ₆ Br ₂	46.7	17.2
MnL ₆ I ₂	42.3	20.4
MnL ₆ (NO ₃) ₂	7.0	17.1
[Me ₃ N][MnLCl ₂]	20.4	39.1

Cur = *Curvularia*

Hs = *Helminthosporium sativum*.

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References

1. G. R. CHAUDHURY and K. C. DASH, *Transition Metal Chemistry*, 1977, **2**, 253.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1959.
3. F. J. WELCHER, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Van Nostrand, New York (1947).
4. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.* 1964, **6**, 102.
5. J. LEWIS and R. J. WILKINS, "Modern Coordination Chemistry" Interscience, New York, 1960, p 403.
6. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
7. L. T. TAYLOR, N. J. ROSE and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.* 1968, **7**, 785.
8. J. L. BURMEISTER, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1966, **1**, 205.
9. L. E. MOORE, R. B. GAYHART and W. E. BULL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 896.
10. B. J. HATHAWAY, D. J. HOLAH and M. HUDSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 4586.
11. M. R. ROSENTHAL, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1973, **50**, 331.
12. N. F. CURTIS and Y. M. CURTIS, *Inorg. Chem.* 1965, **4**, 804.
13. C. C. ADDISON and D. F. SUTTON, *Progr. Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **8**, 1169.
14. B. M. GATHHOUSE, S. E. LIVINGSTONE and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4227.
15. R. S. DRAGO, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold, New York, 1965.